

NEWSLETTER

CONCILIARE: keep up with our progress!

Welcome to the sixth edition of our newsletter!

As the CONCILIARE project progresses, recent activities and events have helped keep partners and collaborators connected, supported by extensive dissemination efforts across the countries involved. On 2 October, the first project assessment provided a valuable opportunity to review achievements, identify upcoming challenges, and highlight areas for improvement. Congratulations to all for the work accomplished so far — let's continue striving for the best results!

NEWS

Decolonial perspective in Belgium with Afropean

On 21 September, the Afropean Project team spent a few hours around the controversial sculpture “Maroon slaves caught by dogs”, in Brussels, to gather the impressions of residents and passers-by.

These voices and testimonials will be heard in the podcast ‘(Not) In my neighbourhood’, which is currently in production. Over the last months, the team also conducted interviews that will feed into this podcast, with guests such as Alana Castro Azevedo and Chantal Kesteloot.

In addition, the Afropean Project has launched a series of workshops, which will continue until May 2026, bringing together professionals in the field of decolonial guidance. They aim to share experiences and reflections on what decolonial guidance is, whether it is carried out in museums exhibiting colonial heritage or in the streets of cities and countries whose colonial past is highlighted during guided tours.

Stay tuned: a handbook will present the results of these exchanges, aiming to inspire both professionals and museums.

Understanding Through Difference. The Museum and Otherness

Our colleague Emiliano Abad, from the University of Coimbra, represented CONCILIARE in the roundtable held on 1 July, at the Museo Nacional Thyssen-Bornemisza in Madrid, Spain. The event centred on the idea of “the Other” in the museum - the one who looks, who observes, or the one that exists because the museum seeks to conquer them and persuade them through its narrative.

The discussions aimed to reflect on the kinds of otherness museums are constructing today. Watch the whole talk below!

PAST EVENTS

Audiovisual Heritage Meetings in Maputo, Mozambique

From 27-31 October, the city of Maputo, Mozambique, hosted the third edition of the Audiovisual Heritage Meetings. The event promoted discussions on audiovisual heritage, historical memory and education through a programme including thematic panels, exhibitions, workshops, debates, guided tours, book launches and film screenings.

This initiative was organised by the Association of Friends of the Cinema Museum in Mozambique (AAMCM), with support from the Calouste Gulbenkian Foundation, in partnership with CECS-UMinho, as part of the CONCILIARE project, among other entities.

Rosa Cabecinhas was part of the panel “Cinema, history, education and research” at the French-Mozambican Cultural Centre, an opportunity to debate the role of cinema in narrative construction and to foster historical awareness and intergroup dialogue.

She was also interviewed by Rádio Moçambique, the national broadcaster of Mozambique, and by Rádio Cidade Maputo, during which she presented CONCILIARE's goals and its contributions to a more plural and inclusive public memory.

1st International Afro-Tourism Meeting in Portugal

On behalf of the CONCILIARE project, the team from the Centre for Social Studies (CES), represented by Sebastián Zuñiga and Djuzé Neves, participated in the 1st International Afro-Tourism Meeting in Portugal, entitled “Afro-Tourism: New Opportunities for the Portugal–Brazil Market (Connecting Cultures and Celebrating Roots)”.

Organised by Diaspora.Black, the event took place on 7 November at the Embratur and ApexBrasil headquarters in Lisbon. The panel “Experiences of Afrotourism in Portugal” showcased the potential of afrotourism to share historical knowledge through the memories and experiences of Afro-descendant communities in the country.

What do we do with this? Thinking about colonial issues

To promote discussion on pervasive colonial legacies and contribute to the decolonisation of knowledge and public space, this debate series took place from 20-21 November in Braga, Portugal, as part of Braga'25 – National Capital of Culture, in partnership with CONCILIARE.

The event stems from the project "What do we do with this?", which brings together young artists, activists, scholars, and individuals with diverse experiences related to colonial issues. The group's work has resulted in multiple artistic outputs, including a book featuring original stories and illustrations, a collective performance inspired by the book and an audiovisual art installation. Thus, this work was shared with the public, alongside a decolonial tour in Braga and discussions curated by CONCILIARE, in collaboration with the MigraMediaArts project and the Communication and Society Research Centre (CECS) of the Institute of Social Sciences, University of Minho.

UPCOMING EVENTS

International Workshop - Textbooks and Voices in Contemporary Europe

On December 4th and 5th, the University of Coimbra will host the International Workshop “Textbooks and Voices in Contemporary Europe” on behalf of the CONCILIARE project.

Over two days, interview projects conducted in Finland, Italy, and Portugal will be presented, and the results and their implications for history education, developed within Task 1.2, will be discussed. The invited experts, Mario Carretero and Karel van Nieuwenhuysse, will also engage in a roundtable on history education, offering international and multidisciplinary perspectives on the teaching and representation of the colonial past.

2nd International Social Psychology Workshop

COLONIAL LEGACIES:
Textbooks and Voices in Contemporary Europe

4 de dezembro, das 9h às 11h. 5 de dezembro, das 9h30 às 10h30

Faculdade de Psicologia e de Ciências da Educação.
Universidade de Coimbra, Edifício I.

Participação gratuita com inscrição:
<https://qrco.de/bgOOPx>
Com certificado de participação

Funded by the European Union

The sessions are open to everyone, aiming to make this research project accessible to a broader audience and to encourage dialogue on the education of colonial history. In parallel, the participating experts will meet to advance Task 1.3, focused on developing a pedagogical tool.

COLLOQUE
« Héritages coloniaux en Belgique »
INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
"Colonial Legacies in Belgium"

28 JAN : Conférence d'ouverture - Opening lecture
29 JAN : Panels "Controverses postcoloniales" et "Ex-coloniaux" - Panels "Postcolonial Controversies" and "Ex-Colonials,"
30 JAN : Panels "Décolonisation de l'espace public" et "Universités et histoire coloniale" - Panels on "Decolonization of Public Space" and "Universities and Colonial History."

28,29 & 30 JAN 2026
ULB, Campus du solbosch
Batiment S, Salle Somville

Co-funded by the European Union

REGISTRATION

Conciliare's annual meeting & International Conference "Colonial Legacies in Belgium"

We are about to enter 2026 with special activities: from 28-31 January, the city of Brussels will gather CONCILIARE's members over two events organised by the Université Libre de Bruxelles (ULB) team. One is our project's second annual meeting, which will be held at the ULB campus - Solbosch Campus, Building S, Somville Room.

Simultaneously, the International Conference "Colonial Legacies in Belgium" will be held at the same venue. This event is organised in partnership with the ARC-HERICOL research project (GERME, AGS, LAMC).

Save the date and we'll see you there!

Thank you for your continued support and engagement in CONCILIARE!

Paula Di Leone, Rosa Cabecinhas, Teresa Forte and Emiliano Abad

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